

G'O'ZA HOSIL ELEMENTLARINING SHAKLLANISHI

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ABSTRACT

Bentonitdan qishloq xo'jaligida foydalanishning ilmiy jihatlari maqolada batafsil bayon etilgan. Bentonitning kimyoviy tarkibi va paxta yetishtirishda qollanishining ijobiy tomonlari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Go'za chigitlarini sho'rlangan tuproq sharoitida bentonit bilan ishlov berish hosildorlik va sifat ko'rsatkichlarini oshiradi.

G'o'zaning o'sib rivojlanishi har oyning birinchi sanasida amalga oshirilgan fenologik kuzatuv va biometrik o'lchashlar natijasiga ko'ra variantlar orasidagi farq tahlil etib borildi. Tajriba dalasining barcha variantlarda bir xil agrotexnik tadbirlar qo'llanilib, o'g'itlash va sug'orish me'yor va muddatlari ham bir xil belgilandi. Shunga qaramasdan, chigiti qobiqlab ekilgan hamda bargidan oziqlantirishda bentonit gillari kukunidan foydalanilgan paxta maydonlari nazoratga nisbatan sezilarli darajada farq qildi. Bundan tashqari alohida ta'kidlash kerakki, joriy yilda yurtimizda g'o'zaning o'sib rivojlanishi iyul oyida haroratning o'ta yuqori bo'lishi g'o'zaning o'sib rivojlanishida ancha qiyinchiliklar tug'dirdi.

G'o'zaning Buxoro-102 navi ekilgan tajriba dalalarida 1-iyun, 1-iyul va 1-avgustdagi kuzatishlar olib borilganda g'o'zaning bo'yi nazorat paykalchalarida, ya'ni, chigit toza holda ekilgan variantda mos ravishda 19,1, 65,7, 102,6 sm ni, chigit bentonit gillari bilan qobiqlab ekilgan paykalchalarda 20,8, 69,8, 115,3 sm ni, chigitni qobiqlash bilan birgalikda bargidan bentonitli suspenziya bilan oziqlantirilgan variantlarda 21,8, 72,8, 120,5 sm va faqatgina bentonitli suspenziya bilan oziqlantirilgan variantlarda esa 20,7, 71,5, 113,7, 120,5 sm ni tashkil etdi.

Bir o'simlikdagi chinbarglar soni chigitni qobiqlash bilan birgalikda bargidan bentonitli suspenziya bilan oziqlantirilgan variantlarda nazoratga nisbatan 1,7 taga ko'p bo'lganligi aniqlandi, hosil shoxlari ham aynan shu variantda yaxshi ko'rsatkichlar berdi, ya'ni, 1-iyulda 2 taga oshgan bo'lsa, keyingi oyda shu ko'rsatkich 4,3 tagacha oshib borishi kuzatildi, hosil elementlari esa shu 2 oyda 2,9 va 3,7 taga ko'p bo'ldi (4.3-jadval).

Buxoro-6 va Buxoro-8 navlari ekilgan tajriba dalalarida ham aynan shu 3-variantda qo'llanilgan ekishdan oldin chigitni bentonit gillari kukuni bilan qobiqlash va bargidan oziqlantirilganda bentonit va karbamidli suspenziyadan foydalanish g'o'zaning bo'yiga, hosil shox va hosil elementlarining

shakllanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi (4.3-jadval).

G'o'za hosildorligi

Urug'ning sifati, chigitni ekish muddati va miqdori, tuproqning meliorativ holati, unumdorligi kabi ko'rsatkichlar bilan bir qatorda vegetasiya davri davomida olib borilgan agrotexnik tadbirlar paxta hosiliga bevosita o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi.

Tajribalarimizda qo'llanilgan bentonit gillari kukuni bilan qobiqlab ekish hamda bargidan oziqlantirilganda mineral o'g'itidan tayyorlangan suspenziyaga bentonit gillari kukunini aralashtirib sepish usullari qo'llanilgan variantlardagi paxta hosilida sezilarli o'zgarishlar kuzatildi.

Buxoro-102 navida hosildorlik ko'rsatkichi nazorat variantida 38 s/ga bo'lgan bo'lsa, chigiti qobiqlab ekilgan variantda 41,9, chigiti qobiqlab ekilgan va bargidan bentonit+karbamidli suspenziya bilan 3 marta oziqlantirilgan variantda 45,2 hamda faqatgina bentonit+karbamidli suspenziya bilan bargidan 3 marta oziqlantirilgan variantda 42,5 s/ga paxta hosili olindi. Bu esa o'z navbatida nazoratga nisbatan mos ravishda 3,9, 7,2 hamda 4,5 s/ga yoki 10,2, 18,9 hamda 11,8% qo'shimcha hosil olinganligidan dalolat beradi.

Xuddi shunday, hosildorlik ko'rsatkichi Buxoro-6 navida nazoratga nisbatan mos ravishda 2,8, 5,7 va 3,7s/ga yoki 9,2, 18,7 va 12,2 % hamda Buxoro-8 navida 2,8, 4,5 va 3.1s/ga yoki 10,0, 16,6 va 11,4 % qo'shimcha hosil olishga erishildi (4.4 -jadval).

Xulosa o'rnida aytish mumkinki, bentonit gillarining yuqorida keltirilgan xususiyatlari tajribalardagi paxta xosilida ham o'z ijobiy natijalarini berdi. Mavsum davomida 4 marta emas, 3 marta sug'orish bilan, ya'ni, 700-1000 m³ gacha sug'orish suvlarini tejagan holda ham bentonit gillaridan foydalangan holda yuqori hosildorlikka erishish mumkin.

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